

STUDY OF RARE FORMS OF BREAST CANCER IN UZBEKISTAN

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Cost: Breast cancer (BS) is a heterogeneous disease with expression subtypes of tumors known to date. Despite the progress made in prevention, diagnosis and treatment, this pathology continues to take the leading place among all malignant tumors and remains the main cause of death.

Purpose: to study rare histological types of breast cancer in Uzbekistan.

Materials and methods: in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as statistical data show, this pathology remains in the top three among all malignant tumors in the last few years. According to the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 3030 patients with breast cancer were identified in 2019, their incidence rate is 19.2, for comparison in Russia it is 53.6; 23.1 per 100,000 populations in the world; In 2019, 1,645 patients with breast cancer died in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the mortality rate was 10.3; Russia 13.5; the world was 13.0.

According to 2020 data, the first cases of breast cancer in Uzbekistan were 3317, the incidence rate was 9.8 per 100,000 populations and 19.5 per 100,000 women. In 2020, 63.0% of malignant mammary tumors were diagnosed in stages I-II, 24.1% in stage III, and 10.3% in stage IV. 1,578 people died from breast cancer, with a mortality rate of 4.7 per 100,000. By the end of 2020, the number of breast cancer patients at the dispensary was 20,861, with a 5-year survival rate of 45.1%. The highest rate of breast cancer in women is in Tashkent (50.4), Bukhara (26.3) and Tashkent (21.5) regions, and the lowest is in Surhandarya (11.1), Kashkadarya (12.5) and Namangan (13) ,3) regions.

Results: The analysis of a nature data showed that the more frequent morphological forms of BS are more studied and are being actively studied. In this regard, interest in various aspects of the problem of development of rare forms of breast cancer does not subside. The need to distinguish rare forms of BS is related to their clinical direction, histological structure, receptor status, growth rate, specific characteristics of the tumor, metastatic potential, metastasis, chemical resistance, etc. The incidence of cancer of this localization, according to different authors, ranges from 4.1 to 25%. Rare cancer accounts for 12.7% of all breast cancer cases. At the same time, we could not find enough generalizing information about rare forms of breast cancer, its treatment and treatment results in Russian and foreign sources.